

ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF SHEA (VITELLARIA PARADOXA) STEM AND
ROOT FOUND AT IGBOPE, ORELOPE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF OYO
STATE, NIGERIA USING PARTICLE INDUCED X-RAY EMISSION (PIXE)
TECHNIQUE

BY

Adedamola David ALADESE

A RESEARCH THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS
AND ENGINEERING PHYSICS, FACULTY OF SCIENCE OBAFEMI
AWOLOWO UNIVERSITY, ILE-IFE, OSUN STATE

NIGERIA

IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF
BACHELOR OF SCIENCE (B.Sc.) DEGREE IN ENGINEERING PHYSICS

JUNE 2015

CERTIFICATION

The undersigned hereby certify that this work is an original research carried out by Adedamola David ALADESE with the registration number PHY/2010/015 in the Department of Physics and Engineering Physics, Faculty of Science, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. To the best of our knowledge, similar work has not been submitted elsewhere for an award of a degree.

.....

Dr. C. A. Aborisade
(Supervisor)

.....

Date

DEDICATION

I dedicate this project to Elyon – God most High and to my dear mother, Mrs. Caroline Durodola Aladese.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

My greatest appreciation goes to God most high, the creator of the universe for all He has done for me throughout my duration in this great citadel of learning.

I will also appreciate my supervisor, DR. C. A Aborisade for his support, patience and words of encouragement for the successful completion of this thesis; he is a father and a rare gem among men.

My expression of gratitude also goes to all lecturers in the department for the knowledge gained and the culture learned throughout my stay on campus.

My special thanks go to my beloved parents for their support and special care towards my academics and also to my siblings, Aladese Lekan Michael and Akinfolarin Oluwaseun Marvelous.

Finally, my sincere appreciation to my project partners Adeyemo Ayodeji, Amurawaye Thaddeus and Azeez Tola. To my good friends Salau Hamudat Oyiza, Obadiya Tomilola Medetin, Sidney Jonathan and Igbekele Temitope; I am saying a big thank you for making the department a more conducive place for me. I really appreciate Olabiyi Olaoluwakiitan Olabiyi as well for the words of encouragement, inspirations and for your time.

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ABSTRACT

Studies have shown that the shea (*Vitellaria paradoxa*) tree is an important ecological, nutritional and socio-economic resource for upgrading the standard of living of the indigenous population in Guinea and Sudan Savannah zones of Nigeria.

However, little is known about the essential elemental concentration profile of the shea stem and root. It is obvious that apart from the nutritional and medicinal properties of shea nut tree, the evidences on its economic and environmental importance to the economy of the nation are enormous.

This study is aimed at determining the elemental composition of shea stem and root using PIXE technique and to use 1.7 MV Pelletron Tandem accelerator of Center for Energy Research and Development (CERD) at Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife for the sample analysis.

The elements present in the shea root sample are Mg, Al, Si, P, S, Cl, K, Ca, Ti, Mn, Fe and Sr. From the analysis, potassium has the highest concentration while Manganese has the least concentration. The shea stem sample on the other hand contains the following Mg, Al, Si, P, S, Cl, K, Ca, Ti, Mn, Fe, Sr, and Ba. The elemental concentrations range from the highest to the lowest showing that the shea stem contains high concentrations of calcium and manganese has the least concentrations.

The results obtained were within the World Health Organization (WHO) / Recommended Daily Dietary Allowances (RDA) standards. This data is paramount in the estimation of essential minerals dietary intake for humans as well as its significance in research, medical purposes, and in the industry.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview of Shea Tree

The Shea tree (*Vitellaria paradoxa*) is one of such indigenous wild fruit trees with enormous nutritional benefits. The Shea nut tree is an economic crop indigenous to the Guinea and Sudan savannah zones of Nigeria. It is grown between latitudes 70N -120N. Its role in food production, foreign exchange earnings, raw materials for industries, income and employment generation to millions of Nigerians most especially women and young people makes it a crucial asset for National Economic Development. It is obvious that apart from the nutritional and medicinal properties of Shea nut tree, the evidences on its economic and environmental importance to the economy of the nation are enormous.

1.1.1 Shea tree Names

Different names are used for the Shea (*Vitellaria paradoxa*) Tree in literatures and in some part of the World. Some of these names are used in this thesis, the botanical names are:

Vitellaria paradoxa, *Lucuma paradoxa*, *Butyrospermum paradoxum*, *Bassia parkii* and *Butyrospermum parkii*

Other names:

Shea Butter tree (English), Se (Bambara), Ka'danya (Hausa), Kareje (Fulani), Lulu (Arabic), Karité (French), Igi Ori (Yoruba)

1.1.2 The Botany of the Shea Tree

Shea trees belong to Sapotaceae family and were first named by the German botanist Carl Gaertner (Gaertner, 1807) as *Vitellaria paradoxa* sub species *paradoxa* and *nilotica*.

It is perennial and deciduous. Mature tree height vary considerably with some trees attaining heights of over 14m and girth of over 1.75m (Yidana, 1994). The tree has profuse branches with a round or hemisphere crown. The bark of the stem is conspicuously thick, waxy, corky and deeply fissured that makes it fire and termites resistant. The abundance of the Shea tree in Nigeria exists in and thrives almost exclusively in the North.

1.1.3 Shea Tree Growth and Development

They mostly grow naturally in the wild; the long period taken to reach maturity has discouraged its planting in an organized plantation. The Shea or Karite, formally *Butyrospermum* produces its first fruits (which resembles large plums) when it is about 20 years old and reaches its full production when the tree is at about 45 years old and continue to produce nuts for up to two hundred (200) years, after reaching maturity.

In the wild, Shea trees grow up to 9-12 m (30-40 feet) in height and begin to bear commercial quantities of fruit after approximately 20 to 50 years (Tella, 1979; RAISE, 2002). Shea trees do not reach maturity until 45 years and after getting mature, they can continuously produce Shea nuts for up to 200 years (RAISE, 2002; Alander, 2004). Compared to other trees grown as plantation crops, Shea trees take much longer time to reach maturity, which have discouraged the commercial plantation.

It is easy to understand how longer it takes for Shea trees to reach maturation by simply comparing with coffee trees (*Coffea Arabica*). *Coffea Arabica* is commercially important coffee species belonging to Rubiaceae family and originated in South Western Ethiopia

(Steiger *et al.*, 2002). Coffee plants in Salvador are reported to begin to bear after 2 to 3 years and reach full maturity after 7 to 8 years and continue to yield coffee beans up to nearly 30 years (Ukers, 1922). For this reason, the entire Shea industry is based upon Shea butter collected in many countries from naturally growing stands of Shea trees.

Shea trees blossom during February to March, and the fruit become matured in June to July (Alander, 2004). The fruit are harvested during June to September once they fall to the ground from the trees (RAISE, 2002; Alander, 2004).

Method of Propagation

1.1.4.1 Propagation by Seed

Shea is naturally propagated by seed as it ripens and drops on moist ground.

- The seed is recalcitrant; viability falls rapidly a week after removal from the fruit and is lost completely within 3-6 weeks.
- Germination is cryptogean; that is, the shoots arise from below ground even though the seed germinate on the surface.

1.1.4.2 Propagating Shea by Grafting

- Grafting of Shea saplings consists of joining together a live branch from a mature tree (scion) to the rootstock of a sapling so that they may grow together as a single plant.
- The practice of grafting on Shea can help reduce the long gestation (maturity) period of the tree.

1.1.4.3 Propagation by Air Layering

- Air-layering is an ancient method used to propagate a number of tropical and subtropical trees and shrubs including Shea
- It is a process of removing a large branch or section of the trunk of a tree to create another tree
- Before the branch is removed it is girdled, wrapped with peat moss or other media and then sealed with plastic and the girdled section is allowed to root. After rooting the branch is removed from the tree.

Figure 1.1: Villateria Paradoxa Tree

1.2 Shea Fruit

Shea fruit is light green coloured with a diameter of 2-3 inches or 5-8 cm as seen in fig 1.2 (Chalfin, 2004). Shea fruit consist of a green epicarp (the outer part), a fleshy mesocarp (pulp), and a relatively hard endocarp (shell) containing embryo (Shea kernel) (Olaniyan *et al.*, 2007). Mostly, Shea fruit contain one or two kernels but occasionally have two to three from which Shea butter is extracted (Alander, 2004).

The fruit consists of a green fleshy mesocarp, which is sweet when eaten and in very ripe fruits seems to melt on the tongue when the fruit is bitten. The fruit is edible with a nutritious sweet and spice able flavour pulp. The fruit pulp is also a source of food for other animals such as elephants, sheep, pigs, bats and birds (USAID, 2004). Apart from the fruit playing an important role in the diets it is also sold in local markets (FAO, 2007), it is also used to make jam.

1.2.1 Uses and Benefits of Shea Fruit

The fruit when very ripe is either eaten as a snack, but it is also a famine food. It can be eaten raw or lightly cooked. The pulp can be processed into juice. It serves as food to both animals.

The Shea fruits constitute a great source of essential nutrients such as vitamins, mineral, carbohydrates, crude fibre and proteins (Okullo *et al.*, 2010). Like other edible fruits, Shea fruits are also rich in different carbohydrates such as glucose, fructose and galactose (Neuwinger, 1994)

Figure 1.2: Shea Fruit

1.3 Shea Butter

While the tree has so many uses, it is well known for the production of Shea butter. Shea butter production involves various stages, beginning with de-pulping, to get rid of the fleshy fruit.

This is achieved by fermentation which is enhanced by initial boiling or burying the fruit. Following de-pulping, the nuts are sun-dried for five to ten days. When temperatures are below 50 degrees Celsius, drying can go on for several days but at 50 degrees Celsius, the desired moisture content of six to seven percent is archived between four to five days.

The nuts are de-husked through trampling, pounding them in a mortar using a pestle or crushing them using two stones to get rid of the brown cover leaving only the kernel. The kernel is then crushed and baked or roasted over carefully monitored heat to prevent it from being charred since charred kernels would lower the quality of Shea butter produced by reducing its fat content. Roasting promotes fat concentration and latex coagulation and prolongs the shelf life of the nuts. Those that attain a moisture content of seven percent after roasting can be stored for two years. Extracting butter from the baked kernel involves grinding it into a fine powder which is then mixed with warm water.

The resulting semi-solid mixture is then kneaded or stirred continuously to form a paste. The paste is left standing and with time oil collects on it which is collected periodically, finally leaving behind a brown residue after all the oil has been collected.

Figure 1.3: Shea Butter

1.3.1 Uses of Shea Butter

Shea butter has long been used in the West African countries, used for cosmetic uses. Many records on traditional uses of Shea butter have focused on its ethno-pharmacological uses.

1.3.1.1 Traditional and Industrial Uses of Shea Butter:

Shea butter is used by local healers as a treatment for rheumatism, inflammation of the nostrils, nasal congestion, leprosy, cough, and minor bone dislocation (Tella, 1979; Badifu, 1989; Goreja, 2004; Olaniyan, 2007).

Shea butter has also been used for soothing and accelerating healing after circumcision, and for preventing stretch marks in African pregnant women (Goreja, 2004), which is frequently mentioned on the advertisement of Shea butter products.

Shea butter has also been used to massage newly born babies. In addition, Shea butter has been used as an insect repellent, providing protection against *Simulium* infection (Goreja, 2004).

In addition to the ethno pharmacological uses, Shea butter has been used in West African cuisine as edible oil due to its high nutritional value and affordable price (Kar *et al.*, 1981; Njoku *et al.*, 2000; Chalfin B. 2004; Olaniyan, 2007).

Shea butter is used as the base of many soups and condiments (Goreja, 2004). For example, when Shea butter is mixed with onion and pepper, it becomes a popular condiment (Chalfin B. 2004). Beverages made with Shea butter combined with millet flour, water, and savory spices have been served during weddings, funerals, and work parties (Chalfin B. 2004).

Shea Butter is very good in Skin, scalp, and hair emollient and moisturizing activity. Using Shea Butter aids anti-aging of skin due to protease-inhibiting activity, Sun-screening function.

Shea-butter or Shea oil is used in factories to produce baking fat, margarine, cocoa butter substitutes and various moisturizing beauty and pharmaceutical products.

1.4 Shea Tree root and the Stem:

In Nigeria, the roots of the Shea nut tree are used as chewing sticks especially in the savannah areas. The roots and the root bark are sometimes ground into a paste and taken orally as a cure for jaundice in Ghana as well as the treatment of diarrhoea and stomach ache. Nonetheless, the tree can also be employed by the unscrupulous for foul means. Among the Jukun tribe of Nigeria, the roots are mixed with tobacco to produce poison. The Shea stem bark is termite resistant and is used in poles building.

1.5 Benefits of the Shea Tree

The husks make a good mulch and fertilizer (FAO, 1988), and are also used as fuels on three stone fires. Shea leaves are used as medicine to treat stomach ache in children (Millee, 1984). In horses, chronic sores are treated using boiled and pounded root bark of this plant (Dalziel, 1937).

Infusions of the bark have shown to have selective anti-microbial properties, as being effective against *Sarcina lutha* and *Staphylococcus aureus* but not mycobacterium (Soladoye et al., 2000). Macerated with the bark of *Ceiba pentandra*, and salt, bark infusion have been used to treat cattle with worms in the tundra region of Senegal and Guinea (Ferry et al., 1974).

The infusions have been used to treat leprosy in Guinea Bissau (Daziel, 1937) and for gastric problems (Booth and Wickens, 1988) as well for diarrhoea or dysentery. A bark decoction is used in Cote d'ivoire in baths and therapeutic sit-baths to facilitate delivery

of women in labour, and is drunk to encourage lactation after delivery (Abbiw, 1990; Loupe, 1994).

However, in northern Nigeria such a concoction is said to be lethal (Daziell, 1937). A bark infusion is used as an eye wash to neutralize the venom of spitting cobra and also, in Ghana, as a footbath to help extract jiggers. Greenwood (1929) noted that the stripping of the bark for medical purposes may have a severe impact on the health of Shea trees and may even be fatal. The wood is used only when the individual Shea tree is not valued for butter production. This is because of the long gestation period of the tree crop as such farmers are reluctant to cut down any tree unless it is proven to be of inferior value for butter production.

The latex is heated and mixed with the palm oil to make glue. It is chewed as a gum and made into balls for children to play with (Louppe, 1994). In Burkinafaso, musicians use it to repair cracked drums and punctured drumheads (Millee, 1984). It contains only 15 to 25% of carotene and, therefore, is not suitable for the manufacture of rubber.

1.6 Justification and Relevance of this Study

Shea tree is an economic crop; it has varieties of elemental composition and mineral contents. This study is carried out to determine the elemental composition in the stem and root of the Shea Tree and to educate people concerning the nutrients and benefits from these.

Also, the result from this research will be more relevant if certain elements which are not present in the Shea fruit and butter as seen from researchers work are present in the samples (Shea stem and root), as this will lead to more healthy benefits to the nation as a whole.

1.7 Aim

The aim of this study is to determine the elemental compositions of the Shea root and stem using Proton Induced X-ray Emission (PIXE) technique

1.8 Objectives

The specific objectives of this research work are:

- I. to use the 1.7MV Pelletron Tandem accelerator of Center for Energy Research and Development (CERD) at Obafemi Awolowo University Ile-Ife, Osun State in the elemental analysis of Shea tree root and stem
- II. to obtain a result showing concentrations of elements collected as spectra carrying information on the chemical composition of the sample.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

A lot of research works have been carried out on Shea nut fruit, Shea butter and the flowers among others, as there were no much study on research on the Shea tree root and the stem. Elemental analysis of Shea tree root and stem using PIXE technique is relatively new and first so far, making this research a very unique one.

This literature review includes research work on Shea nut shells, Shea tree latex, Shea butter, refined and unrefined Shea butter, Shea fruit pulp and the Shea Butter Oil using different analysis and tests.

2.1 Determining the Chemical Structure and Composition of Biomass Fuels Using X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)

Guilin et al., (2004) carried out a research on the chemical structure and composition of Shea nut shells using X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS). Shea nut shells are an example of an agricultural residue by-product of food and feed production of potential interest for biomass combustion. The X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) can provide fundamental knowledge of their structures that is useful in understanding and predicting their combustion behaviour. The XPS spectra of Shea nut shells provide both its elemental composition and indications of its bonding.

At the end of his research, Shea nut shells contain major elements which are Carbon and Oxygen with Nitrogen as the only minor element. This implies that Shea nut shells can be used as a biomass fuel (Biofuel)

2.2 Productivity of Crops in an Agro Forestry System of Shea Trees

A research was carried out in Northern Benin to assess the influence of Shea tree canopy on productivity (height, yield, fresh biomass) of cotton and Sorghum in the study area Césaire et al; (2012).

The presence of trees among crops creates landscapes known as “agro forestry landscapes”. Planting of crops for instance, help maintain soil fertility and the sustainability of cropping systems.

In their research, they found out that the combination of Shea with other crops is common and the effects of inter-cropping Shea trees with other crops appear to be contradictory. The combination of cotton, sorghum and Shea is one of the most common farming systems in northern Benin. They were able to show that the Shea tree canopy has a negative influence on plant height for cotton and sorghum, as well as bud yield for cotton plants.

Though there was a marked improvement in soil moisture and soil fertility under the Shea tree canopy. But, the canopy also helps conserve use of soil water as temperatures are moderate under Shea trees due to shading.

They concluded that the productivity parameters for sorghum and cotton (plant height, yield and fresh biomass) are higher for plants grown outside the Shea tree canopy than those under the canopy. Shea trees adversely affect crop development under the canopy but it is favourable to plant crops that can tolerate the shade such as chilli pepper, a very important food crop as this will increase the yield of the food crops.

The advantage of tree crop intercropping therefore lies in maintaining soil fertility and the sustainability of farming systems, especially since many authors have found that Shea trees are excellent fertilizers thanks to their leaf biomass. Studies report that trees in fields have positive effects on soil fertility, and especially on levels of organic matter and nitrogen; their areas of influence represent “islands” of fertility in semi-arid zones.

Similarly, a research work carried out by Bayala, et al; (2002) in Saponé in Burkina Faso showed that mulch from Shea leaves induced a 120% increase in millet grain yields and a 43% increase in its total dry matter. Shea leaves contribute to soil fertility.

2.3 Preliminary Chemical Analysis of Shea Butter Tree Latex

The chemical analysis of Shea butter tree latex was carried out by Soile et al; Shea butter tree latex collected from two localities in Zaria, Nigeria namely Shika and Bassawa were investigated. The results obtained from classical non-instrumental analysis of latex compares favourably well with what was obtained from infrared and nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopic analysis. A rough estimate of molecular mass of Shea butter latex was determined by viscosity experiments and various components of Shea butter tree latex and their percentage compositions were also determined.

To achieve this, different types of analysis were carried out, such as *preliminary chemical analysis* which comprises the flame test, pyrolysis, boiling with 80% sulphuric acid and *elemental analysis*, the Lassaigne’s test was the basis for the elemental analysis were carried out. Some physical properties of the Shea butter tree latex such as pH, specific gravity, viscosity, were also investigated for characterisation purposes as well as giving a general account and economic importance of the tree.

At the end of their research, it could be concluded that Shea butter tree latex is a mixture of a long chain hydrocarbon macro molecule, resinous extract which is responsible for most of the rubber-like properties shown by the latex, moisture and impurities. The presence of unsaturation in the macromolecule was determined by chemical analysis and confirmed by Weber test and infra red spectroscopy.

From their research, they were able to arrive at a rough molecular weight of the Shea butter tree latex which indicated that the solidified latex is a macro molecule. The combination of these results of infra red and nuclear magnetic resonance analysis of the solidified latex led to the conclusion that the solidified latex belongs to the group of long chain unsaturated hydrocarbon macro molecule.

2.4 Proximate and Chemical Composition of Shea Fruit Pulp in the Guinea Savannah of Nigeria

Indigenous tree fruits in the African parklands such as the Shea fruits constitute a great source of essential nutrients such as vitamins, mineral, carbohydrates, crude fibre and proteins (Okullo et al., 2010). Like other edible fruits, Shea fruits are rich in different carbohydrates such as glucose, fructose and galactose (Neuwinger, 1994).

The proximate analysis showed the moisture content of Shea fruit pulp to be between 14.90-15.54%. The required moisture contents of Shea butter destined for cosmetic and food industries are 0.05% and less than 0.2 %, respectively (Kassamba, 1997). This result indicated low shelf life of the fresh plant hence long storage would lead to spoilage due to its susceptibility to microbial attack. This supports the practice of storage in dry form by users.

Moisture content is among the most vital and mostly used measurement in the processing, preservation and storage of food (Onwuka, 2005).

A significant variation was exhibited in carbohydrate content ($P \leq 0.05$) for the genotypes across the different agro ecological zones in the Guinea savanna of Nigeria. Carbohydrate values obtained in this study was 55.35-59.11%. Shea fruit has more carbohydrates that are vital in nutrition and are also good sources of energy (Anhwange et al., 2004).

Chemical analysis revealed that acid value and peroxide value ranged between 1.54-2.40 mgKOH/kg and 3.52-7.02 meq/kg, while saponification and iodine values were between 131.54 mgKOH/g and 146.29 mgKOH/g and 36.9 I₂/100 and 52.2 I₂/100 g respectively. The proximate and the chemical composition values obtained in this study showed that the Shea fruit pulp is rich in protein, total carbohydrates crude fibre and chemical values

Results of the analysis of variance showed that the mean squares for agro ecology were highly significant ($p \leq 0.05$) for proximate (crude protein, crude fibre, crude lipid and ash) and chemical (acid value, peroxide value, iodine value and saponification value). Total ash, fats, crude fibre, crude protein and total carbohydrate, ranged between 5.1-7.3, 17.28-19.22, 9.0-11.55, 6.24-8.36 and 55.35-9.11, respectively.

The proximate and the chemical composition values also indicate that the Nigerian Shea fruit pulp has adequate nutrients equivalent to other edible fruits, thus growing of Shea butter tree and consumption of its nutritious fruits should be promoted.

More so, the consumption of the Shea fruit pulp after hard labour, thus, provides an immediate source of energy for the farmers. This, therefore, justifies the promotion of consumption of Shea fruits in the Shea zones of Nigeria and beyond.

2.5 Nutritional and Some Elemental Composition of Shea Fruit Pulp

The oven dried Shea (*vitellaria paradoxa*) fruit pulp were analysed for its nutritional composition and some elemental constituents, Aguzue (2013).

The proximate composition values obtained showed that the fruit contained high value of carbohydrate 72.02%, the values of protein and crude fat agree with the values (2.6-7.0% and 0.7-1.7%) reported by *Baiyeri et al;(2008)* while the carbohydrate was high and crude fibre rather low but within range when compared with other agro forestry specie such as the star apple(*chrysophyllum albidum*) and Africa pear (*Dacryodes edulis*) with values 4% and 17.9% respectively as reported by *Baiyeri et al;(2008)*

Some of the mineral constituents analysed are reported, Calcium has the highest content and iron with the lowest value. The result of calcium, manganese and magnesium shows similar values with the one reported by *Maranz et al; (2004)* and other mineral varies. The varied levels of these minerals could be as a result of variation in some climatic factors and may also be due to the different rates at which the elements are taken up from the soil by the plants.

The result showed mean value as moisture 4.58%, ash 8.95%, crude fat 1.35%, crude protein 3.5%, crude fibre 9.6% and carbohydrate 72.02%. Results of mineral analysis showed that calcium had the highest concentration of all the elements analysed and were found to be of the order: Ca > Ni > Co > Mg > Pb > Mn > Fe > Cd. These values suggest that the fruit can be used as nutrient supplement and as a source of micro and macro elements to the body.

Results from the present investigation shows that the fruit is of good nutritional value and a viable source of minerals in the body. It is also expected that the fruit will yield a greater amount of energy considering the relationship between carbohydrate and energy.

Its nutritional potential is suggestive of the fact that it helps to alleviate hunger in the rural area during and after (when preserved) it's ripening season.

2.6 Physico - Chemical Characteristics of Shea Butter Oil

Shea oil is a vegetable oil obtained from the seeds of the Shea tree (*Vitellaria paradoxa*). It constitutes an important source of fat in food and cosmetics. Although Shea oil can be marketed both locally and internationally, increasing demand worldwide for exportable products calls for their certification. Characterization of Shea oil is one step towards developing its certification system.

In this study carried out by Okullo et al; (2010), the physico-chemical characteristics of Shea oil in different Shea zones of Uganda as a case study were assessed. Seed oil was extracted by Soxhlet apparatus using n-hexane solvent and analysed for colour, refractive index, viscosity, oil content, acid value, peroxide value, saponification value, iodine value, α -tocopherols and fatty acid profile.

Shea oil content, colour, refractive index and viscosity ranged from 41-54%, orange to orange–yellow, 1.670-1.690 and 2.4-2.8cP, respectively. Acid and peroxide values ranged between 2.3-12.59 mgKOH/kg and 2.10 to 2.50 meq/kg, respectively. Saponification, iodine and α -tocopherols values were between 160 mgKOH/g and 192mgKOH/g, 39.21 I₂/100 and 41.37 I₂/100g and 26.3-44.4 mg/100g, respectively. Fatty acid profile for palmitic, stearic, oleic, linoleic and arachidic fatty acids ranged between 6.52-8.12%, 28.65-30.94%, 55.54- 57.63%, 6.18-7.79% and 0.65-0.90%, respectively.

Although there was significant variation in the oil yield ($P \leq 0.05$), the physico-chemical characteristic and fatty acid profile showed no significant variation.

The fact that physico- chemical characteristics of Shea oil from the different Shea zones of the area of study are comparable to other high value edible vegetable oils indicates its suitability as raw material for food, cosmetic and pharmaceutical products.

This characterization is a bench mark for monitoring the quality of Shea oil and can be used to enhance its local and international trade. The characteristics exhibited by the physico-chemical composition and fatty acid profile of Shea oil from Uganda make it a possible and potential raw material for cosmetics, soap, food processing (as edible vegetable oil) and in the bakery/confectionery sector.

2.7 Determination of Trace Elements in Shea Butter and Shea Nut by Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA)

While the Shea tree has so many uses, it is well known for the production of Shea butter. Shea butter production involves various stages, beginning with de-pulping, to get rid of the fleshy fruit. This is achieved by fermentation which is enhanced by initial boiling or burying the fruit. Following de-pulping, the nuts are sun-dried for five to ten days.

When temperatures are below 50 degrees Celsius, drying can go on for several days but at 50 degrees Celsius, the desired moisture content of six to seven percent is archived between four to five days. The nuts are de-husked through trampling, pounding them in a mortar using a pestle or crushing them using two stones to get rid of the brown cover leaving only the kernel. The kernel is then crushed and baked or roasted over carefully monitored heat to prevent it from being charred since charred kernels would lower the quality of Shea butter produced by reducing its fat content. Roasting promotes fat concentration and latex coagulation and prolongs the shelf life of the nuts. Those that attain a moisture content of seven percent after

roasting can be stored for two years. Extracting butter from the baked kernel involves grinding it into a fine powder which is then mixed with warm water. The resulting semi-solid mixture is then kneaded or stirred continuously to form a paste. The paste is left standing and with time oil collects on it which is collected periodically, finally leaving behind a brown residue after all the oil has been collected.

With all these, a research was carried out by Adazabra et. al; (2013) to determine the concentrations of trace elements in Shea nut and Shea butter using Ghana as a case study.

As part of the study, measurements of the elemental composition of Shea butter and Shea nut samples were carried out by Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA) using the Ghana Research Reactor-1 (GHARR-1). Samples collected from local markets in the Northern region of Ghana and the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Standard Reference Material (SRM) 1547 Peach leaves were irradiated at the GHARR-1 facility. Validation of the method was done using NIST SRM Orchard Leaves (1571) under the same experimental conditions.

Six trace elements (Na, Mn, Al, Cl, Ca and K) were detected with maximum concentration of Na found to be 15 ± 1 mg/kg in SN5, Mn; 7.4 ± 0.8 mg/kg in SN6, Al; 259 ± 3 mg/kg in SN1, Cl; 666 ± 27 mg/kg in SN1, Ca; 0.21 ± 0.04 wt.% in SN4, K; 2.0 ± 0.04 wt.% in SN1, Ce; 3.2 ± 0.06 mg/kg in SN2, Se; 0.12 ± 0.004 mg/kg in SN4, and Sc; 0.40 ± 0.02 mg/kg in SN2 . The concentrations of the trace elements were within the limit laid down for safe human consumption. Neutron activation analysis based on thermal neutrons from a low power nuclear research reactor, the Ghana Research Reactor-1 (GHARR-1) in combination with a high-purity germanium detector was used to analyse Shea nut and Shea butter samples obtained from local markets in the Northern Region of Ghana. Shea butter is the main edible oil for the people of

northern Ghana, being the most important source of fatty acids and glycerol in their diet (Fobil *et al.*, 2002).

The concentration of the following trace elements; Na, Mn, Cl, Al, Ca, K, Ce, Se, and Sc were determined as part of existing research in establishing baseline levels of essential, non-essential and toxic elements in Ghanaian food items (Nyarko *et al.*, 2006). The elemental concentrations were found to be generally higher in the Shea nuts than the Shea butter. It was also observed that the essential elements were in fair quantities.

2.8 Effect of using vegetable oils as quenching media for pure commercial Aluminium

This work was carried out by Adekunle *et al.*, (2012) and it presents the effects of rate of heat extraction by groundnut, melon, palm kernel, Shea butter and palm oils on the mechanical properties of various samples of pure commercial aluminium heat treated at 200°C, 250°C, 300°C and 350°C. Muffle furnace equipped with digital thermometer and thermocouple was used for the heat treatment.

Tensile strength and hardness tests were carried out using Instron Universal Tester and Vickers hardness methods, respectively. Results obtained from the experiment were presented graphically.

The results showed that palm kernel oil cools faster at 200°C and 250°C, while palm oil and Shea butter oil quench faster at 300°C and 350°C, respectively. Palm kernel oil offers the highest elongation at 200°C, while at 350°C Shea butter oil gave the best result.

The best among the bio-quenching oils in providing good ductility is Shea butter oil at 200°C, while at 300°C and 350°C groundnut oil give the best result. Highest hardness values were obtained from samples quenched in melon oil between 200°C-300°C.

2.9 Quality Characteristics Of West African Shea Butter And Approaches To Extend Shelf-Life

This study was carried out by Hee Seung (2011). Shea butter is a versatile plant fat extracted from kernels of Shea nuts, seeds of Shea trees (*Vitellaria paradoxa*). Shea butter has long been used in sub-Saharan Africa for medicinal, culinary, and other applications and serves as a cocoa butter equivalent in the manufacture of chocolate as well as an ingredient in cosmetics. Shea butter, rich in unsaturated fatty acids undergoes hydrolytic and oxidative degradation during post-harvest processing and storage, resulting in inconsistent and degraded quality and limited shelf-life.

The objective of his study was to assess important quality characteristics of Shea butter. Seven West African Shea butters were analyzed to measure physicochemical parameters by wet chemical tests and to measure chemical composition by gas chromatographic analysis. Physical properties were consistent among samples and within the range of typical Shea butter. The samples also shared similar chemical compositions, showing palmitic (3.36-4.44 % of total fatty acids), stearic (39.74-44.62 %), oleic (40.71-44.48 %), and linoleic acids (5.73-6.41 %) as the major fatty acids and α -amyirin having anti-inflammatory property (57.26-64.37 % of total sterols and triterpenes) as the major unsaponifiable matter.

Moisture, insoluble impurities, free fatty acids, and peroxide values were needed to be controlled. Free fatty acid level was the most variable parameter, ranged from 1.07 to 8.56 %. Peroxide value was low enough except the one which was as high as 15.32 mEq/kg. Total unsaponifiable matters were measured lower (2.21-4.18 %) compared to the previous studies (4-11 %) but still higher than many other plant oils and fats (~2 %).

This study also aimed at identifying the protective effect of selected synthetic (BHT) and natural (rosmarinic and gallic acids) antioxidants on Shea butter from oxidation. Peroxide value, conjugated dienes, thiobarbituric acid reactive substances, and the amount of major fatty acids were measured as oxidative parameters at 0, 72 and 144 hours while the control and samples with 0.02 % of antioxidants were stored at 90 °C with air flow. The antioxidants were significantly effective in protecting Shea butter from oxidation and no significant difference in the effect of synthetic and natural antioxidants was found.

Shea butter showed relatively high amount of unsaponifiables compared to other plant derived oils and fats and the major constituent was found to be α -amyrin which was reported to exhibit anti-inflammatory properties. This characteristic can be used to develop new products using Shea butter or Shea butters unsaponifiable fraction, even though more research is needed on the bioactivity of Shea butter and its isolated triterpenoids and phytosterols.

While it was observed that processing practices can affect oxidation parameters of Shea butter, the addition of natural and synthetic antioxidants can delay the oxidation of Shea butter and thus extend its shelf life.

2.10 Difference between Unrefined Shea Butter and Refined Shea Butter

Shea butter has a multitude of natural healing benefits; Anti-aging, stretch mark treatment, moisturizing, sun-protection, & anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory, to name a few.

In a study carried out in Ghana, it was found out that to receive all these benefits of Shea butter, the unrefined kind is the best compared to the refined Shea butter. All Shea butter is initially extracted from the African Karite (Shea) Nut tree.

Unrefined Shea Butter can either be extracted by hand using traditional West African methods, or with the use of a mechanical press to speed up the process. Both methods produce Shea butter and Shea oil without the use of chemicals or synthetics. The end product is known as unrefined Shea, raw Shea butter, or virgin Shea butter and has the highest concentration of antioxidants, healing benefits and natural UV protection. It can range from beige to light yellow in color and has a slight naturally occurring smokey or nutty aroma. Unrefined Shea that is bright yellow has an added root extract that gives it its deep golden color.

Refined, or ultra refined Shea butter, is extracted and processed with high heat and chemical solvents such as hexane. It is usually pure white in color and contains no odour. Though refined Shea may contain some moisturizing properties, most all of other healing benefits found in the original butter have been lost. Nearly all mainstream products that use Shea butter in their formula are made with refined or ultra refined Shea butter due to its longer shelf life, pure white color, and lack of odour. It can also be easier to work with, having already been heated to high temperatures; refined Shea doesn't get grainy when reheated. These products can be okay moisturizers, but they are a far cry from organic skin care.

All the healthy benefits of Shea butter can be gotten from the unrefined kind, so this make it possible to be used as a skin care, promoting the sales both locally and internationally.

CHAPTER THREE

INSTRUMENTATION AND METHODOLOGY

The full range of analytical techniques with ion beams include many methods based on the same principles; firstly, a beam of MeV ions is aimed at the sample. These projectiles penetrate, losing energy continuously at a well-known rate. Along, there trajectories, there is the chance for collisions which nuclei and with electrons. Secondly, the products of these interactions are emitted from the sample, with probabilities determined by the respective interaction cross sections, and are finally measured and collected as spectra carrying information on the chemical composition of the sample and the elemental depth distributions.

In this project, Particle Induced X-ray Emission (PIXE) technique has been employed for the determination of major, minor and trace constituents of the Shea root and stem respectively. PIXE analysis have been carried out using a 2.5 MeV proton beam generated with the aid of the 1.7 MV Pelletron Tandem accelerator of the Center for Energy Research and Development (CERD) at Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria. With PIXE, one measures X-rays arising from the filling of the inner shell vacancies produced by the projectiles. The X-ray energies are characteristic for the respective elements.

3.1 Tandem Accelerator

Nuclear particle accelerator is a device designed to produce stream of ions that are directed along some path. This is typically achieved by first generating the ions, then causing them to pass through a large electrical potential difference in order to increase their energy even further. From there, a series of magnets are used to direct the high-energy beam towards a “target”.

The beam interacts with the target material, producing radiations that are then made available for some predetermined use.

The 1.7 MV Pelletron Tandem Accelerator at the Center for Energy Research and Development (CERD) is a type of Tandem Accelerators; it is a highly sophisticated nuclear analytical technique equipment, equipped with a RF charge exchange ion source (Alphatross) to provide a proton (H^+) and Helium (He^+) ions. This accelerator has provision for five beam lines ($0^\circ, \pm 15^\circ, \pm 30^\circ$), but the facility at the CERD only operates on the -15° line which is equipped with a multipurpose end station for broad beam ion beam analysis (IBA) namely: Particle Induced X-ray Emission (PIXE), Particle Induced Gamma-ray Emission (PIGE), Rutherford Backscattering Spectrometry (RBS) and Elastic Recoil Detection Analysis (ERDA). For the purpose of this project and the nature of the samples to be analysed, PIXE analysis will be used.

Another Tandem Accelerator is the Van de Graff accelerator with a pair of accelerator tubes. A stripper channel inside the high voltage terminal is used to strip the electrons from the accelerated beam of negative ions.

3.2 Essential Parts of the Tandem Accelerator

The Tandem Accelerator has an insulating Column voltage rating in Megavolts and an ion source that is made up of Alphatross RF system for H^+ and He^+ ions. Other components of the Tandem Accelerator include:

3.2.1 Vacuum Systems

The beam of high energy ions is transported to the target chamber along a drift tube that is maintained at high vacuum. A vacuum between 10^{-3} and 10^{-4} Pa pressures will be sufficient for the minimum collision probability between the fast ions and residual gas molecules. The energy loss for protons will be negligible even at pressures one or two orders of magnitude higher (10^{-1} to 10^{-2} Pa).

Vacuum stations attached to the target chamber or to the drift tubes are consisting of the high vacuum pump and the fore pump, since no single pump has yet been developed which is able to pump down from atmospheric pressure to the high vacuum range. The selection of the pumping principle for the particular application is defined by the main parameters; the lowest pressure, the pressure range, the pumping speed and the exhaust pressure.

Turbo molecular pumps are the most widely used high vacuum pumps today in MeV ion accelerator applications. Easy to operate, they enable fast start, which can be of interest for the use at the target chamber. However, vibrations of the mechanical bearing pumps may affect the semiconductor detector energy resolution. The accelerator tank operates on a vacuum system.

3.2.2 Beam Lines and Target Chamber Materials

The drift tubes (beam lines) and the target chamber are preferably made of materials having low outgassing rate and low vapour pressures. Materials that become part of the vacuum system must also have sufficient mechanical strength to withstand the pressure difference. Stainless steel, glass windows and metal seals are in all respects the best solutions having the lowest outgassing rates. Aluminium chambers with Perspex windows and rubber seals are also

frequently used due to much easier machining, but these are not recommended for the ultra high vacuum. Attached to the beam lines are the beam profile monitor, beam slit and Faraday cup.

3.2.3 Target (Scattering) Chamber

Target chambers are designed for the performance of experiments using charge particle beams. Their characteristics will depend on the requirements determined by the technique for which the chamber is needed. There are numerous desired characteristics of the Target chamber for the measurement.

3.2.4 Collimators

The shape of the beam cross section is defined by a series of collimators. They are typically circular holes of diameter ranging from less than mm to 1 cm, but most often between 3 and 8 mm. Collimators can also consist of two series of x and y slits that can limit the beam to different rectangular shapes. A minimum of two series of collimators is needed, the first collimator or collimators define the beam shape, while the last one is anti-scattering collimator. The anti-scattering collimator reduces the beam that is scattered on the edges of the beam defining the collimator. Without it, the scattered part of the beam can excite X-rays of the elements in a sample frame, chamber and other parts that can be seen by the X-ray detector.

3.2.5 X-ray Detector

The amount of energy of X-ray measured by the radiation detector using scintillator or proportional counters could not be widely used in the past due to their poor energy resolution. By the development of semiconductor detector technology, energy dispersive X-ray

spectrometry (measurement of X-ray energy by radiation detector) became superior in many fields of application and for all types of X-ray excitation (electrons, ions or photons). The semiconductor Si(Li) detectors are the most suitable choice for PIXE analysis, the intrinsic germanium detectors are a second choice of semiconductor detector, with slightly better energy resolution. Unfortunately, higher efficiency for high energy X-ray region (above 20 KeV) will make the COMPTON scattering of particle induced X-rays emitted from the sample much more probable, increasing the background in the final PIXE spectrum.

3.2.6 End Station

It is equipped with a multi-purpose scattering chamber with facilities for Rutherford Back Spectrometry (RBS), Proton Induced X-ray Emission (PIXE), Photon Induced Gamma-ray Emission (PIGE) and Elastic Recoil Detection Analysis (ERDA).

3.3 Data Acquisition Systems

Energy of the detected X-ray is converted in the pulse processing electronics to the voltage pulse delivered at the output of the spectroscopy amplifier. This is an analog signal (pulse amplitude) which has to be converted to a digital number in a device called multichannel analyser (MCA).

3.3.1 Multi Channel Analyser (MCA)

The MCA spectrum consists of a certain number of channels which number is a linear function of X-ray energy. Each channel is actually a counter that counts events in the corresponding energy interval, forming the final energy spectrum on the MCA screen. The key element in a MCA is the analogue to digital converter (ADC) and the storage memory.

3.3.2 Analogue to Digital Converter (ADC)

The ADC output is stored in memory with as many possible addressable locations on the maximum number of channels into which the recorded spectrum can be subdivided. Number of memory locations (channels) is usually made a power of two with 1024 or 2048 channels being the most common choice in PIXE experiments. The important specifications of an ADC are its speed, linearity of conversion and resolution of the conversion. The other ADC feature important in particular for the PIXE analysis is its conversion speed or the ADC dead time. During the conversion, the ADC is unavailable for processing. This type is typically between 10 and 100 micro seconds. It is therefore important to measure the *live* time, to account for lost pulses inhibited while the ADC is dead. In order to account for all contributions to the dead time, inhibit signal from the amplifier has to be connected to the ADC. The total dead time will be superposition of the amplifier and the ADC dead time.

3.3.3 Multi Channel Analyser (MCA) Storage Memory

For the simplest single parameter pulse height analysis, the multichannel analyser is just an electronic module inserted in one of the slots of a personal computer, with an external Analog to Digital Converter (ADC), or ADC being incorporated into the module. The memory needed to store the data is now the main computer memory and the hard disc, while the computer screen is used for the spectrum display.

- PC Cards

The most economical MCAs today are plug-in cards for personal computers providing a computer-controlled data acquisition. Most of these cards have built in ADC, microprocessor and program memory and are generally single input in ADC that can accept inhibit signal from

the pre-amplifier are recommended. Otherwise, PC cards which are able to accept digital pulses from external ADCs are recommended. Other MCA hardware types are Nuclear Instrumentation Module (NIM) and the CAMAC standard.

3.3.4 Multi Channel Analyser (MCA) Software

Data acquisition software today offers many advanced functions that are useful for online interpretation and qualitative analysis of PIXE spectra, Typical functions of interest are:

- Energy calibration, peak search and peak identification
- Peak centroid and peak shape (FWHM) calculations – needed for the energy calibration calculations and energy resolution control
- Calculation of integral or net area counts in the peak by a simple background subtraction and statistical uncertainty
- Different spectrum display features (expand, overlap, logarithm/linear vertical scale, etc.)
- Hardware control features

3.4 Data Analysis Software

The extraction of X-rays peak areas from the PIXE spectrum and their correlation to the concentration of particular element, form the basis of quantitative PIXE analysis. A large variety of PIXE software packages exist today, with most of them available to calculate both X-ray peak areas (intensities) and respective elemental concentrations. There exist many software packages for fitting and/or quantification of PIXE spectra. Some of them are: AXIL,

DATTPIXE, GEOPIXE, GUPIXWIN, PIXAN, SESAMX, TTPIXE, WITS-HEX. The GUPIXWIN data analysis software is used in this project.

3.5 Advantages of PIXE

- Non-Destructive Analysis

It is a non invasive technique and it does not damage the sample being studied (analysed).

- Sensitivity and Spatial Resolution

Few parts per billion (ppb) level measurements for cases like organic liquids and few parts per million (ppm) level measurements for mineralogical and metallurgical samples. In absolute terms, for conventional beam of a few mm in diameter, the detection limit is 10^{-11} gm for micro beam detection limit is 10^{-16} gm. With PIXE, a micro PIXE resolution of less than one micron (10^{-6} m) can be achieved. The PIXE technique is also known for its precision and accuracy.

- Speed

Only a few minutes for sample which may give information about 10 - 15 elements.

- Multi Element Capability

The entire periodic table covered with little variation in sensitivity. Elements below Sodium cannot be detected because they are either absorbed by the detector window or by the filters being used.

- **Versatility**

The technique can be applied to a wide range of material analysis problems. Analysis of all kind of objects, say from a single blood cell to a large painting. It is also used for qualitative and quantitative analysis in Geology, Archaeology, Biology, Materials science and environmental pollution.

3.6 Experimental Procedure

Sample collection, sample preparation and analysis using PIXE technique are discussed in this section. The 1.7 MV Pelletron Tandem Accelerator (Figure 3.1) for the Center for Energy Research and Development (CERD) of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife is used for the PIXE analysis.

3.6.1 Sample Collection

A small portion of the stem and root were cut from the Shea Tree (*Vitellaria paradoxa*) at Igbope town, Orelope local government area of Oyo state and were put into a polythene bag and properly labelled.

3.6.2 Sample Preparation

The shea root preparation procedure is as follows; the soil from the sample was washed off in running distilled water in order to remove the dust and unwanted particles. The sample is then properly dried at room temperature. The shea stem is also washed properly in a distilled water to remove surface dust (and unwanted particles). It is then properly dried at room temperature.

Fig 3.1: The 1.7 MV Pelletron Tandem Accelerator

Both dried samples were ground in an agate mortar (Figure 3.2) separately until they become pulverized. A small quantity of the pulverized samples was poured into a pelletizer which is then pressed by a hydraulic press to make pellets of the samples (about 13 mm in diameter). The samples were then taken to the Tandem Accelerator room for the PIXE analysis.

3.6.3 Sample Analysis using PIXE Technique

A $3\mu\text{C}$ proton beam current was employed and the exposure (irradiation) time was 20 minutes. The proton energy of 2.5 MeV has been chosen based on the Ion Beam Analysis (IBA) from the Center of Energy Research and Development (CERD), and also upon dependence of the limit of detection (LOD) on the atomic number of pure elements, this being minimal for almost all targets in the case of proton of proton energy of 2.5 MeV.

Also, the dependence of the X-ray production cross section on the proton energy and the atomic number of the target were taken into consideration. The detection system included a 10 mm thick Canberra Silicon Lithium Si(Li) detector model ESLX 30 – 50 with an energy resolution of 150 eV at 5.9 KeV for the X-rays and with a 0.025 mm thick beryllium window.

The prepared pelletized shea root and stem samples were mounted in the irradiation chamber at 45° with respect to the beam and the detector's direction. The target chamber has a beryllium window for X-rays of 0.1 mm thickness. The PIXE principle is as follows;

A proton from the Radio Frequency (RF) charge exchange ion source (Alphatross) will accelerate to the ground upon interaction with Rubidium; at the ground, negative ions are produced. This negative ion beam passes through the accelerator tank (operating on vacuum) and it is then accelerated to a high voltage positive terminal at a very high velocity due to the

Figure 3.2: Agate Mortar and Pestle

potential difference. The negative ion beam moving with high velocity pass through a canal where the presence of a gas caused it to be stripped off its electrons and then emerges as a positive ion beam. The positive ion beam then receives an additional (second) acceleration which now returns it to the ground. The positive ion beam is then deflected through some analysing quadrupole magnets before proceeding through the switching magnets where it will be directed to the scattering (target) chambers via the drift tubes (beam lines). The samples are placed in the sample stick which is located at the target chamber. The sample stick is designed to carry 11 samples which are in form of pellets of 13 mm diameter.

The positive ion beam on interaction with the target material (samples), encounters numerous inelastic collisions by sample atoms. The incoming ion beam will cause an electron from the inner shell of the atoms of the sample to be ejected, thereby making the atom excited and creating a vacancy in the inner shell. An electron from the outer shell then fill the vacancy created by the ion beam, the difference in the energy levels between the two shells is emitted as X-rays. This X-ray (characteristics X-rays) emitted is peculiar to each element and are detected by a Si(Li) detector which is cooled by a liquid nitrogen.

The Multi Channel Analyser punch cards with inbuilt analog digital converter (ADC) which are able to accept digital pulses were used in data acquisition. The PIXE setup was calibrated using some pure element standards and NIST geological standard NBS278. The collected X-ray spectra were processed with the aid of GUPIXWIN (Guelph PIXE) software package.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Result

Details of the PIXE spectrum obtained during the bombardment of the samples (Shea root and stem) with a 2.5 MeV proton beam generated with the aid of a 1.7 MV Pelletron Tandem Accelerator of the Center for Energy Research Development (CERD) at Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife are being worked on and then translated into tabular forms showing various elemental concentrations. Peaks in spectrum occur at energies indicative of characteristics X-rays and the qualitative analysis is an easy task in PIXE due to the known dependence of X-ray energies with the atomic number of elements.

The results obtained for the Shea root (Sample ID: SR – PIX) and stem (Sample ID: SST-PIX) samples are given in Tables 4.1 - 4.3 below while Table 4.4 shows the recommended dietary allowance (RDA) for elements which include the age in months (mths) and year (yr) as well as their proportions in milligram and gram per day (mgd/gd).

Table 4.1: Elemental Composition of Shea Root Sample obtained from Igbope, Oyo State

Symbol	Concentration (ppm)	Concentration Error
Mg	783.8	± 133.95
Al	733.2	± 40.03
Si	4333.8	± 54.17
P	1196.5	± 69.16
S	1308.1	± 39.90
Cl	922.6	± 29.52
K	12192.7	± 45.11
Ca	6399.2	± 47.35
Ti	189.6	± 8.10
Mn	16.6	± 3.21
Fe	700.4	± 11.91
Sr	25.9	± 10.88

Sample ID: SR – PIX

Table 4.2: Elemental Composition of Shea Stem Sample obtained from Igbope, Oyo State

Symbol	Concentration (ppm)	Concentration Error
Mg	3372.3	± 157.15
Al	1444.5	± 48.25
Si	6963.4	± 70.33
P	1803.0	± 95.02
S	847.6	± 44.24
Cl	824.8	± 32.25
K	9148.7	± 40.25
Ca	16749.2	± 50.25
Ti	229.7	± 9.67
Mn	31.5	± 4.85
Fe	688.7	± 12.40
Sr	72.4	± 16.71
Ba	318.0	± 61.56

Sample 1D: SST-PIX

**Table 4.3: Comparison between Shea Root and Shea Stem Samples obtained from
Igbope, Oyo State**

Symbol	Concentrations (ppm)	
	SR – PIX	SST-PIX
Mg	783.8 ± 133.95	3372.3 ± 157.15
Al	733.2 ± 40.03	1444.5 ± 48.25
Si	4333.8 ± 54.17	6963.4 ± 70.33
P	1196.5 ± 69.16	1803.0 ± 95.02
S	1308.1 ± 39.90	847.6 ± 44.24
Cl	922.6 ± 29.52	824.8 ± 32.25
K	12192.7 ± 45.11	9148.7 ± 40.25
Ca	6399.2 ± 47.35	16749.2 ± 50.25
Ti	189.6 ± 8.10	229.7 ± 9.67
Mn	16.6 ± 3.21	31.5 ± 4.85
Fe	700.4 ± 11.91	688.7 ± 12.40
Sr	25.9 ± 10.88	72.4 ± 16.71
Ba	-	318.0 ± 61.56

Samples ID: SR – PIX and SST-PIX

Table 4.4: Recommended Daily Dietary Allowances Standard

Recommended Daily Dietary Allowances for Elements								
Life Stage group	Age	Calcium mg/d	Phosphorus mg/d	Iron mg/d	Magnesium mg/d	Chloride g/d	Potassium g/d	Manganese g/d
Infants	0 – 6mths	200	100	0.27	30	0.18	0.4	0.003
	6 mths – 1yr	260	275	11	75	0.57	0.7	0.6
Children	1 -3 yr	700	460	7	80	1.5	3.0	1.2
	4 – 8 yr	1000	500	10	130	1.9	3.8	1.5
Males	9 – 13yr	1300	1250	8	240	2.3	4.5	1.9
	14 – 18yr	1300	1250	11	410	2.3	4.7	2.2
	19 -30yr	1000	700	8	400	2.3	4.7	2.3
	31 – 50yr	1000	700	8	420	2.3	4.7	2.3
	51 – 70yr	1000	700	8	420	2.0	4.7	2.3
	> 70 yr	1200	700	8	420	1.8	4.7	2.3
Females	9 – 13yr	1300	1250	8	240	2.3	4.7	1.6
	14 – 18yr	1300	1250	15	360	2.3	4.5	1.6
	19 -30yr	1000	700	18	310	2.3	4.7	1.8
	31 – 50yr	1000	700	18	320	2.3	4.7	1.8
	51 – 70yr	1200	700	8	320	2.0	4.7	1.8
	> 70 yr	1200	700	8	320	1.8	4.7	1.8
Pregnancy	14 – 18yr	1300	1250	27	400	2.3	4.7	2.0
	19 -30yr	1000	700	27	350	2.3	4.7	2.0
	31 – 50yr	1000	700	27	360	2.3	4.7	2.0
	14 – 18yr	1300	1250	10	360	2.3	5.1	2.6

Lactation	19 -30yr	1000	700	10	310	2.3	5.1	2.6
	31 – 50yr	1000	700	9	320	2.3	5.1	2.6

4.2 Discussion

The elements present in the Shea root sample (SR-PIX) are Mg, Al, Si, P, S, Cl, K, Ca, Ti, Mn, Fe and Sr. The limits of detection (LOD) are between the range 1 – 300 ppm for the elements.

From the results presented in Table 4.1, it can be observed that the concentrations of all the elements. From the results presented in Table 4.1, it can be observed that the concentrations of all the elements analysed ranging from the highest to the lowest shows that Potassium (12192.7 ± 45.11) is the highest and Manganese (16.6 ± 3.21) is the least but Barium is not detected. This shows that the sample is highly important since it has high concentration of useful macronutrients, for example, Potassium together with Calcium and Magnesium help to reduce the blood pressure.

The results obtained are within the RDA standard as showing in Table 4.4, hence it is not toxic, however, it should be properly used in the right proportion. From the research carried out on Moringa roots by Azeez (2015), it was noted that the elemental concentrations of the Moringa root is slightly higher than that of the Shea root. Also, the elements present in the shea stem sample (SST-PIX) are Mg, Al, Si, P, S, Cl, K, Ca, Ti, Mn, Fe, Sr and Ba with the limits of detection (LOD) ranging between 1 – 300ppm.

From the result, Calcium (16749.2 ± 50.25) has the highest concentration of all the elements analysed and Manganese (31.5 ± 4.85) has the least concentration. This shows that the sample is highly significant since it has a high concentration of useful macronutrients, for example, calcium aids bone and teeth development. The results obtained are also within the RDA standard.

Table 4.3 shows the comparison between the shea root and stem samples, it can be observed that Barium, Ba is not detected in the root sample but it is present in the stem. This can be as a result of environmental factors or other factors such as temperature, water transport, light, soil pH and salinity – as this in one way or the other affect the distribution of mineral s and element concentrations of the tree. These factors can also be the reasons why there are variances in element concentrations between the root and stem of the shea tree. The elemental concentrations distribution between the shea root and stem are slightly consistent. For example, the concentrations of potassium and calcium in both samples are very high – with Manganese having the least concentration. However, elements such as sodium, chromium, nickel, rubidium and zirconium are not detected in both samples. It was also noted that the concentration of elements presents in the soil obtained from Igbope are higher than those present in the root and stem obtained from the same location (Adeyemo, 2015). The slight difference in element concentrations between the soil and both samples (root and stem) can be as a result of environmental, chemical and physical factors.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

The presented PIXE technique is known for its sensitivity, accuracy, precision, simplicity of thick target preparation and the ability to perform multi-elemental analysis of a large number of samples, sometimes quickly, requiring small amounts of material.

The results obtained from the samples (Shea root and stem) show that they will be a good dietary supplement since they are within the RDA standard can be therefore serve several medicinal purposes if the elements detected are combined in the right proportion.

The radionuclide concentration of the shea nut from the same location where the samples were gotten from is very low and thereby considered safe (Azuka, 2008). Therefore, since the radionuclide concentration from the study area is low, then both samples can be used as diet supplements when processed and have significant importance in medicine and industrial applications.

5.2 Recommendation

Since this research carried out using PIXE technique and it is so far different from other researchers work – this makes the research unique. The results obtained from these samples will serve as basis for further research.

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